

LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL FEATURES OF ENGLISH SLANGS

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***Abstract** This article deals with the study of the features of the slang in modern English language. The aim of the article is to analyze the linguistic and social features of slangs. The definition of slang begins to attract attention of modern philology. Now there is rather large number of the definitions of slang which are quite often contradicting each other.*

***Key words:** slang, etymology, linguistic feature, social feature, social group.*

Slang is one of the most interesting and at the same time difficult phenomena of language. Many researchers usually carry a slang to social dialects. The dialect in this context is the territorial, temporary or social kind of language. In the English lexicography the term “slang” was widely adopted approximately at the beginning of the last century.

Slang emanates from conflicts in values, sometimes superficial, often fundamental. When an individual applies language in a new way to express hostility, ridicule, or contempt, often with sharp wit, he may be creating slang, but the new expression will perish unless it is picked up by others. If the speaker is a member of a group that finds that his creation projects the emotional reaction of its members toward an idea, person, or social institution, the expression will gain currency according to the unanimity of attitude within the group. A new slang term is usually widely used in a subculture before it appears in the dominant culture. Thus slang—*e.g.*, “sucker,” “honkey,” “shave-tail,” “jerk”—expresses the attitudes, not always derogatory, of one group or class toward the values of another. Slang sometimes stems from within the group, satirizing or burlesquing its own values,

behaviour, and attitudes; *e.g.*, “shotgun wedding,” “cake eater,” “greasy spoon.” Slang, then, is produced largely by social forces rather than by an individual speaker or writer who, single-handed (like Horace Walpole, who coined “serendipity” more than 200 years ago), creates and establishes a word in the language. This is one reason why it is difficult to determine the origin of slang terms.

The etymology of the word “slang” also is disputable. Slang - the complex, difficult and inevitable language phenomenon. Its emergence is always caused by historical, social and cultural tendencies of life of this or that language community. Slang is the diction that results from the favorite game among the young and lively of playing with words and renaming things and actions; some invent new words, or mutilate or misapply the old, for the pleasure of novelty, and others catch up such words for the pleasure of being in the fashion. These similes are so novel and vivid that they can't be made without good imagination, while think-machine (brain), sparkler (diamond), pickers (hands), canned music (musical disk) are more vivid and expressive. Sometimes slang words are invented by a few people for the pleasure of novelty and imitated by others who like to be in fashion. Many of the slang words coined during the Second World War have passed out of use along with the events that called them into life.

The slang is interesting not only from the point of view of the linguistic theory, but also from a translation theory position. The slang words cover almost all spheres of life. The slang is concentrated on the person -spheres of his life, the relations with other people.

The contribution of slang in enriching language; a short of real representation of the dynamism of language and symbol of human freedom in creating language was an interesting phenomenon to be analyzed.

The slang expression means coming to democratic atmosphere in language since the meaning embodied is not absolute. It depends upon who uses it, in which group the users belong to, and in what situation slang word occur. The question

emerged is how the user of slang employ slang in their daily communication. Their choice of certain slang replacing the standard may have certain purposes.

Today, slang is embedded in our culture and people use it everyday even though they might not realize they are using it. But not all US slang is universal either. Slang often suggests that the person utilizing the words or phrases is familiar with the hearer's group or subgroup; it can be considered a distinguishing factor of in-group identity. Different slang is used amongst different cultures, popular interests, occupations or where you live. For example,

The term "freshies" is a word used to describe fresh, untouched snow that fell the night before.

"Pow pow" is also a word used to describe very light, fluffy snow that has the consistency of powder.

"Gondy" is a contraction of the word gondola.

Slang expressions are created in basically the same way as standard speech. As stated in the now discontinued Microsoft Encarta encyclopedia, "expressions may take form as metaphors, similes, and other figures of speech." In addition, it is noted that "the words used as slang may be new coinages, existing words may acquire new meanings, narrow meanings of words may become generalized, words may be abbreviated, etc. However, in order for the expression to survive, it must be widely adopted by the group who uses it."

Slang is a way in which languages change and are renewed. The slang that young people use today is completely different from the slang of decades past. It is even different than the slang that my generation used to use and I am not *that* old. One of the most common slang words in English today is the word "cool,"- something that is excellent or very good. But it wasn't always that way. For example, in the 1950's, young people used the word "swell," to describe good things, a word that is not used today at all in that context. In the 1960's and 1970's, "cool" started to be used but it also morphed into the word "groovy" which also is not used today

amongst popular slang. In the 1980's the word "wicked" or "sweet" was used alongside or instead of "cool." In the 1990's, something cool was also "dope" or "bad" (bad meaning good.) And in the 2000's there is "redic", "redonculous" or "sick" or "whack" and a slew of many other slang words that mean cool, some of which are not appropriate for this article, but you "get my drift" (you understand).

While many slang words introduce new concepts, some of the most effective slang provides new expressions - fresh, satirical, shocking - for established concepts, often very respectable ones. Sound is sometimes used as a basis for this type of slang, as, for example, in various phonetic distortions (*e.g.*, pig Latin terms). It is also used in rhyming slang, which employs a fortunate combination of both sound and imagery. Thus, gloves are "turtledoves" (the gloved hands suggesting a pair of billing doves), a girl is a "twist and twirl" (the movement suggesting a girl walking), and an insulting imitation of flatus, produced by blowing air between the tip of the protruded tongue and the upper lip, is the "raspberry," cut back from "raspberry tart."

In conclusion, the whole world uses slang and everyone should be aware of the slang in their respective languages. Slang is a fascinating phenomenon of language and many universal English slang words are actually now being put in the dictionary and are considered part of the English lexicon, making slang come full circle; starting out as a real word, morphing into a slang word, used so much people have forgotten the original word from where the slang word was derived and finally the slang word is considered a real part of the language.

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